

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF $\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3/\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ NANOCOMPOSITE CERAMICS

Yibin Li¹, Xiadong He¹, Thirumany Sritharan², Yue Sun¹

¹ Center for Composite Materials, School of Astronautics, Harbin Institute of Technology, P.O. Box 3010, Harbin 150080, P. R. China

² School of Materials Science and Engineering, Nanyang Technological University, 50 Nanyang Avenue, Singapore 639798, Singapore

Email Address: liy0003@ntu.edu.sg

The Ti-doped BiFeO_3 ($\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$) powders were prepared by solid state reaction. Multiferroic nanocomposite $\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3/\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ were synthesized by solid state reaction from the precalcined mixture of Bi_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 as starting materials. The nanocomposite ceramics were characterized by XRD, FESEM, XPS techniques. It was confirmed that Fe_2O_3 and $\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ are distributed uniformly in the ceramics. The ferroelectric and ferromagnetic properties were evaluated.

INTRODUCTION

Multiferroic materials that couple electric, magnetic and structural order parameters could result in simultaneous ferroelectricity, ferromagnetism, and ferroelasticity. Among these, ferroelectromagnetics appear to have the best potential for applications in fields such as information storage, spintronics, and sensors. A magnetoelectric (ME) material must exhibit magnetic and ferroelectric ordering independently and simultaneously (multiferroic), but with an additional effect of coupling between the two ordering phenomena. This is interesting both from the point of view of basic

science and the application, and is being paid more much attention in recent years [1,2]. Generally, all the multiferroic materials studied to date can be classified into two types: single phase and composites. The realizable magnitude of the ME voltage coefficient in the single phase materials is thought to be insufficient for practical applications, composites are becoming more attractive because of their relatively high ME effects [3, 4].

Among numerous magnetoelectric composite systems, $\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ is an interesting one since $\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ is a typical ferroelectric with large electric saturation and Fe_2O_3 is ferrimagnetic with large magnetostriction. The large strain involved is thought to be significant as the coupling is theorized to be mediated by the strain/stress effect. This composite of ferroelectric phase $\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ and ferrimagnetic phase Fe_2O_3 can be electromagnetically coupled via stress mediation [5]. As the first model system of magnetoelectric composites, $\text{BaTiO}_3\text{-CoFe}_2\text{O}_4$ has been studied widely since 1970s [6-9]. It was first synthesized by the Philips Laboratory using the unidirectional solidification method. The ME coefficient in such composite material was reported to be about an order of magnitude higher than that of single-phase materials such as Cr_2O_3 . Recently, an experimental breakthrough in depositing multiferroic $\text{BaTiO}_3\text{-CoFe}_2\text{O}_4$ nanostructures in a film-on-substrate geometry [10], in which particularly efficient coupling between two phases was achieved.

In this paper, we proposed a new kind of multiferroic nanocomposite $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3/\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$, which were synthesized by solid state reaction from the precalcined mixture of Bi_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 as the starting materials.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The $\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ (BFO) powders were synthesized by using a high-energy ball milling (60 hours) technique followed by conventional reaction sintering at 800°C for half an hour. The magnetic phase Fe_2O_3 was commercially available (AlfaAesar). 80 wt% $\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ (BFO) and 20 wt% Fe_2O_3 composites were ball milled for 20 h and sintered at 600°C for half an hour. Simultaneously, a pressure of 30 MPa was applied to compress the disk-like sample for characterization and electrical properties testing.

Some sintered powders were characterized by X-ray diffraction (Shimadzu 6000 diffract meter) at a scan rate of 1 deg/min and at 0.02° steps with $\text{Cu } K_\alpha$ incident radiation. Some pellets were polished, etched and coated for microstructure and composition observations by scanning electron microscopy (JSM-6340F) with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). Magnetic properties were measured in a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM, Lake Shore 7404) at room temperature up to a magnetic field up to 10 kOe, using the sintered powder. The ferroelectric test was carried out in a Radiant Technologies hysteresis loop tracer at room temperature with a maximum applied electric field of 35 kV/cm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

X-ray diffraction patterns of the as-milled and sintered BFO samples are shown in Fig 1. The as-milled sample shows that the powder are more amorphous, implying there is no reaction occurred between the two phases but to some extent the powders were amorphousized. However the sample conventionally sintered at 800°C showed

some changes in purity and crystal structure. When there is no Ti doped into BiFeO_3 powder, the BFO phase is monoclinic, as shown in Fig 2 (a) where the peaks show doublet characteristics. However, when 10at% Fe was doped into BiFeO_3 , the crystal structure of BFO changed into tetragonal structure, as shown in Fig.2 (a). This can be more clearly seen from Fig. 2 (b) where the 2θ range is zoomed in: without Ti doping there are two peaks at around 32 degree while there is only one peak when Fe is added into BiFeO_3 . This means that Fe substitution causes the phase transformation in BiFeO_3 .

Fig.1: XRD of as-milled, sintered conventionally, and SPS samples.

The SEM images of the sintered BiFeO_3 sample with and without Ti doping are shown in Fig 3 as secondary electron micrographs. Note the presence of the finer phase is observed in the BiFeO_3 sample without Ti doping. However, it seems that the impurity disappeared after Ti doping, which is in consistency with XRD results. In the lower magnification micrographs, the BFO and Fe_2O_3 phases give different contrasts, as shown in Fig. 3 (c) and (d). The distribution of phases appear to be

uniform in conventionally sintered samples but varied at different locations in the sintered samples. Compared to the surface, the centre of the sample showed a finer phase structure with greater uniformity of phase distribution.

Fig. 2 XRD patterns of BiFeO₃ powder with and without Fe dopant: (a) large scale scanning; (b) magnified pattern near 32 degree

Fig. 3. SEM micrographs of the polished surfaces of the BiFeO_3 ceramics: (a) without Ti doping and (b) with doping; (c) and (d) $\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3/\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ composites.

The ferroelectric test was performed on the thin bulks with two silver electrodes, which were immersed into silicon oil for preventing arc. The plot of polarization versus applied field is shown in the Fig. 4. The hysteresis loops confirm the ferroelectric nature of composites. We can also observe that the saturation polarization (P_s) was decreased when Fe_2O_3 was added to form composite.

Hysteresis loops typical of ferromagnetic materials were evident in all samples at room temperature. Fig. 5 shows the B-H curves for samples before and after sintering. Fig 5(a) compares the as-milled $\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ and $\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3/\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$

composite powder. Obviously, the addition of Fe_2O_3 significantly increases the magnetization property. After sintering, both $\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ and $\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3/\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ powders show increased and saturated hysteresis loop, as evident in Fig. 5 (b). Also, the $\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3/\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ composite has higher saturation magnetization than $\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$. Note that the coercivity has significantly decreased on sintering but the saturation magnetization has increased. This could be attributed to the extremely high defect population expected in the as-milled material. Such defects are resistance centres for domain wall movement which is the reason for increase in coercivity. All sintered samples generally gave low coercivities and comparable saturation magnetization but the differences in their saturation levels are measurable.

Fig. 4: Ferroelectric polarization loops of (a) $\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$, (b) $\text{BiFe}_{0.9}\text{Ti}_{0.1}\text{O}_3/\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ composites

Fig. 5: The typical B-H curves of as-milled and sintered samples: (a) as-milled BiFe_{0.9}Ti_{0.1}O₃ and BiFe_{0.9}Ti_{0.1}O₃/Fe₂O₃ composite powder; (b) sintered BiFe_{0.9}Ti_{0.1}O₃ and BiFe_{0.9}Ti_{0.1}O₃/Fe₂O₃ composite powder

CONCLUSIONS

The Ti-doped BiFeO₃ (BiFe_{0.9}Ti_{0.1}O₃) powders were prepared by solid state reaction. Multiferroic nanocomposite Fe₂O₃/BiFe_{0.9}Ti_{0.1}O₃ were synthesized by solid state reaction from the precalcined mixture of Bi₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ as starting materials. The Ti doping causes the phase transformation in BiFeO₃. It was confirmed that Fe₂O₃ and BiFe_{0.9}Ti_{0.1}O₃ are distributed uniformly in the ceramics. Fe₂O₃/BiFe_{0.9}Ti_{0.1}O₃ shows both ferroelectric and ferromagnetic properties.

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